

SARS-CoV-2/COVID-19 a basic and global approach to the pandemic.

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Abstract.

Since 1966, the first coronaviruses to cause any pathology in humans have been described, however it was not until 2002 that a coronavirus caused a highly pathogenic disease such as SARS-CoV. We have currently experienced a pandemic caused by another of these coronaviruses, SARS-CoV2. The objective of this document is to present global information about this pandemic, from its origins, as well as its possible clinical manifestations, its empirical treatment and the measures that we can adopt to improve diagnosis and prevent disease, or in some cases prevent lethality. through the use of measures such as basic measures and vaccines that have been developed in the short time that we have known about this new virus.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Origin of the Pandemic

In 1966, according to the literature, the first coronaviruses that cause any affection in humans were described, these being the Human Coronavirus (HCoV). The types HCoV-E229 and HCoV-OC43 were the most frequent and also affected the respiratory system, causing acute seasonal infections. This classification also includes HCoV-NL63 and HKU1 described in 2005¹.

Until before 2002 the types that had affected humans were not considered highly pathogenic, however, the perspective changed when Three coronaviruses that have crossed the species barrier managed to cause fatal pneumonia in humans²., It all started in the Guangdong province of China in 2002 when the severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus (SARS-CoV) emerged, in 2012 in the Arabian Peninsula the respiratory Middle East appeared. coronavirus syndrome (MERS-CoV)³ and again in December 2019, in Wuhan, Hubei, China, cases of pneumonia of unknown cause appeared, with symptoms compatible with cases of viral pneumonia. At that time, analytical tests were carried out on samples obtained from the lower respiratory system, which led to the discovery of a new coronavirus, which was named new coronavirus 2019 (2019-nCoV or SARS-CoV) due to its characteristics and its year of appearance. (two)⁴.

In January 2020, the WHO (World Health Organization) stated that, according to conclusive evidence, the outbreak originated in the "Wuhan Seafood Market"⁵. On March 11, 2020, the director general of the WHO, Tedros Adhanom, in a press conference stated and announced that the new Wuhan disease was no longer a focused infectious source, and raised the term "PANDEMIC".⁶.

B. What is SARS-Cov-2?

This is a virus belonging to a large family of viruses that has the ability to cause disease in both animals and humans. In our species, it is known for certain that there are several strains of coronaviruses that can cause predominantly respiratory diseases that can have a natural history of a common cold, even making patients severely ill.⁷

The new coronavirus roughly belongs to the family Coronaviridae, of the genus Betacoronavirus⁸, However, if we want to know their classification better, we can say that according to the tenth report of the International Committee on Virus Taxonomy (ICTV), coronaviruses are classified in the following order:

- **Nidovirales**, which have 3 sub-orders: **Abnidovirineae**, **Arnidovirineae**, **Cornidovirineae**.
- The sub order Cornidovirineae presents a Family called **Coronaviridae**
- The Family **Coronaviridae** presents 2 subfamilies: **Letovirinae**, **Orthocoronavirinae**.
- The **Orthocoronavirinae** subfamily has 4 genera: **Alphacoronavirus**, **Betacoronavirus**, **Deltacoronavirus**, **Gammacoronavirus**.
- The genus **Alphacoronavirus** has 2 subgenera: **duvinacovirus** and **setracovirus**.
- The **betacoronavirus** genus has 3 subgenres: **Embecovirus**, **Merbecovirus**, **Sarbecovirus**.
- The **duvinacovirus** subgenus includes species such as **HCoV-229E**
- The **Setracovirus** subgenus presents species such as **HCoV-NL63**
- The **embecovirus** subgenus presents species such as **HCoV-HKU1** and **Betacoronavirus 1**
- The **marbecovirus** subgenus presents species like **MERS-CoV**

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- The **SARS-CoV** and **SARS-CoV-2**
- The **Sarbecovirus** subgenus presents species such as: especie **betacoronavirus** presents subspecies as **HCoV-OC43**⁹

Figure 1. classification of coronaviruses according to the tenth report of the International Committee on Taxonomy of Viruses.

This new coronavirus has an average incubation period of 5 days¹⁰, being its longest incubation period of 14 days, being similar to SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV¹¹, being its longest incubation period of 14 days, being similar to SARS-CoV and MERS-CoV

Genomic studies of the genetic material of Covid 19 indicate that its possible origins are through a zoonosis of the Bat or Pangolins, and its form of transmission is through droplets of saliva that travel approximately half a meter before falling to the ground., being its main entrance door the mucous membranes.

II. CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS

According to the WHO (World Health Organization) the new Coronavirus disease presents a series of symptoms that are very similar to those caused by any other respiratory entity, due to this the clinical diagnosis of it may be affected¹².

The phase of transmission or contagion from person to person occurs 24 to 48 hours before the onset of symptoms and this can last an average of 7 to 9 days after the onset of symptoms. It has also been considered in estimates that a A single case can lead to 2 to 3 new cases¹.

Because of this we can classify the clinic in two:
Patients with mild symptoms:

- Cough
- Headache
- Pharyngitis

Patients with Severe Symptoms:

- High fever
- Dyspnea at rest

Which appear between a period of 5 to 6 days, but can go up to 14 days and even 1 day after exposure¹³.

A study from King's College London revealed that there are 6 types of symptomatic coronavirus patients¹⁴.

1. "Influenza-like" without fever: Headache, anosmia, myalgia, cough, pharyngitis, chest pain, without fever.
2. "Flu-like" with fever: headache, anosmia, cough, pharyngitis, hoarseness, fever, anorexia.
3. Gastrointestinal: headache, anosmia, anorexia, diarrhea, pharyngitis, chest pain, no cough.
4. severe level 1, fatigue: headache, anosmia, cough, fever, hoarseness, chest pain, fatigue.
5. severe level 2, confusion: headache, anosmia, anorexia, cough, fever, hoarseness, pharyngitis, chest pain, fatigue, confusion, myalgia.
6. severe level 3, abdominal and respiratory: headache, anosmia, anorexia, cough, fever, hoar-seness, pharyngitis, chest pain, fatigue, confusion, myalgia, dyspnea, diarrhea, abdominal pain.

III. LABORATORY DIAGNOSIS

A. Generalities

There are different ways to demonstrate or detect the coronavirus, of these there are two types of tests to detect COVID-19 that are available: viral tests and antibody tests. (15)

- A viral test shows if you currently have an infection.
- Antibody tests can tell if you have ever had an infection.

The viral load tests that exist in our environment are the RT-PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction, Reverse Transcriptase), carried out using nasal or throat samples, which must be carried out in all those patients suspected of Covid, being very effective in detecting active disease by SARS-CoV-2, however, even if the test is Negative, the patient must be isolated and the test repeated because it has high rates of false negatives¹⁶.

B. What is RT-PCR?

The study of RT-PCR or reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction, is a test or technique used for the identification and amplification of viral RNA, which allows scientists to study the expression of certain genetic characters¹⁷.

Unlike the simple PCR that only includes 3 steps, the RT-PCR includes 2 extra steps, which will be described below:

- Step 1: RNA is extracted from the cells under Study, in this case from COVID-19
- Step 2: Complementary DNA (cDNA) is transcribed from each RNA molecule by an enzyme called reverse transcriptase.
- Step 3: the cDNA molecules are denatured, through the use of temperature, which oscillates between 95°C and 95°C, favoring the breaking of the Hydrogen bonds that make up the double strand of the molecule.
- Step 4: now the initiators must be aligned, so temperature is still used, however, in this step the temperature is usually lowered to a value between 50°C and 70°C.
- Step 5: now we proceed to amplify the cDNA, through the use of temperature and another enzyme, this time with a temperature of 72°C and a polymerase enzyme. This step is repeated 20 to 30 times to have enough material to study.

Figure 2. Stages or steps of the Reverse Transcriptase Polymerase Chain Reaction Process (RT-PCR).

IV. OTHER TESTS

The Antibody and Antigen Tests that we currently handle in the Environment are Rapid Tests such as the Nasal Pharyngeal Swab, which searches the nasal or pharyngeal mucosa for residues of SARS-CoV-2 antigens for rapid detection, the test gives its results in approximately one hour or less, this can be very effective in detecting that there was an infection by SARS-CoV-2, however it cannot detect if it is active, if the result is negative it is recommended to complement it with a viral test as is RT-PCR.¹⁸

The Antibody Elisa test is another of the tests to detect SARS-CoV-2 which is performed by obtaining blood and usually gives results between 1 to 3 days, however, although it has greater sensitivity than the pharyngeal nasal swab test, it is necessary to repeat the test to obtain more accurate results, this

test is used to detect the active virus in the host or to detect that the patient does not have the disease¹⁸.

V. IMAGE DIAGNOSTICS

A. CT

The chest CT has a sensitivity of 77% and a specificity of 96% for the diagnosis of COVID-19, due to which a study was carried out that showed that the main findings in the CT are¹⁹.

- Opacities in Ground Glass
- Frosted Glass with Consolidations
- Adjacent Pleural Thickening
- Air Bronchogram

These findings being more frequent in the right and left lower lobes, and less frequent in the upper lobes.

Figure 3. CT: with evidence of ground glass opacities (thin arrow) and consolidation with the presence of air bronchogram (thick arrow). Taken from BMC pediatric. 2020; 20 (227) 1-8.²⁰

Figure 4. CT image without contrast in a 50-year-old woman with a mild form of COVID-19. Asthma patient with no respiratory symptoms except fever. Her husband has recently been diagnosed with COVID-19. CT shows ground glass opacities in both upper lobes, some in the subpleural region (arrowhead) and others more centrally distributed (arrow)²¹.

VI. PREVENTION

Because the main vector of contamination is found in the drops of saliva that we expel when speaking and its entrance door is the mucous membranes, the main prevention measures that have been proposed are the following::

1. Hand washing 5 moments WHO
2. Use of Surgical Mask or Kn95
3. Protective Glasses or Face Protection Mask
4. Disposable Surgical Cap (In the environment of Hospital personnel)
5. Waterproof surgical gown (In the environment of Hospital Personnel)
6. Disposable Surgical Shoes (In Hospital Personnel environment)
7. Use of Alcohol/Chlorine Combinations for surface disinfection.

Having already applied primary prevention measures, we have to talk of the next protective measure than that of vaccination.

VII. COVID-19 VACCINES

Vaccines approved in America for the treatment of COVID-19²²:

1. Pfizer-BioNTech (BNT162b2)
2. Moderna (ARNm-1273)
3. ChAdOx1-S AstraZeneca (AZD1222 Vaxzevria™,(SII COVISHIELD™)
4. Janssen A d26.CoV2.S
5. Vacuna de Sinopharm:
6. CoronaVac de Sinovac
7. Bharat Biotech BBV152 (COVAXIN®)
8. Ad5-nCoV-S de CanSino Biologics (Convidecia ®)
9. Valneva (VLA2001)
10. Novavax NVX-CoV2373

The Vaccines approved in the European region for treatment and prevention of COVID.19 are the following²³:

1. Comirnaty® Original/Omicron BA.4-5
2. Spikevax® Moderna mRNA
3. Vaxzevria® (SII COVISHIELD™)
4. Janssen A d26.CoV2.S
5. Novavax® NVX-CoV2373

Other Vaccines used in Covid-19

1. Sputnik V
2. Sputnik Lite
3. Soberana
4. Abdalah

VIII. TREATMENT

There is still no treatment for Covid-19, however, therapeutic alternatives are sought that are useful to treat the symptoms and prevent the natural progression of the disease and avoid complications and therefore the death of the patient, among the treatments that usually serve as treatment²⁴:

- Ivermectin: 6mg tablets, Mild case 2 tablets orally a single dose, moderate case 2 tablets orally per day for 2 days, severe case 4 tablets orally on day 1 and then 2 tablets orally per day for 6 days²⁵
- Nitaxozanide: 500 mg orally every 12 hours for 5 days

However, we can include the treatments in treatment schemes which can be depending on the severity of the symptoms of the patients.

Patients with mild symptoms:

Scheme 1

1. Paracetamol tab 500mg PO every 6 hr x Fever
2. Acetyl Cysteine on 600 mg in water ID x 5D
3. Acetylsalicylic acid tab 100mg PO ID x 7 D
4. Nitaxozanide tab 500mg PO every 12 hr x 5D

Scheme 2

1. Ivermectin 12mg PO ID Single Dose
2. Acetaminophen tab 500mg PO every 6 hr x Fever
3. Acetylcysteine on 600 mg in ID water x 5D
4. Acetylsalicylic acid tab 100mg PO ID x 7 D
5. Nitaxozanide tab 500mg PO every 12 hr x 5D

Scheme 3

1. Ivermectin 12mg ID Single Dose
2. Acetaminophen tab 500mg PO every 6 hr x Fever
3. Acetylcysteine on 600 mg in ID water x 5D
4. Acetylsalicylic acid tab 100mg PO ID x 7 D

Patients with moderate symptoms

Scheme 1

1. Acetaminophen tab 500mg PO every 6 hr x Fever
2. Acetylcysteine on 600 mg in ID water x 5D
3. Enoxaparin 40mg/0.4mL ID SC x 5D
4. Nitaxozanide tab 500mg PO every 12 hr x 5D

Scheme 2

1. Ivermectin 12mg PO ID x 2D
2. Acetaminophen tab 500mg PO every 6 hr x Fever
3. Acetylcysteine on 600 mg in ID water x 5D
4. Enoxaparin 40mg/0.4mL ID SC x 5D
5. Nitaxozanide tab 500mg PO every 12 hr x 5D

Scheme 3

1. Ivermectin 12mg PO ID x 2D

2. Acetaminophen tab 500mg PO every 6 hr x Fever
3. Acetylcysteine on 600 mg in ID water x 5D
4. Enoxaparin 40mg/0.4mL ID SC x 5D
5. Azithromycin tab 500mg PO ID x 7D

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